

E-Government System for Park Use Permission Services with a CRM Approach at the Tangerang City Government

¹Imam Halim Mursyidin, ²Dede Irawan, ³Doni Prasetyo

Faculty of Engineering *Sheikh Yusuf Islamic University, Tangerang, Banten, Indonesia*

E-mail : ¹*imamhalim@unis.ac.id*, ²*dedeirawan@unis.ac.id*, ³*doniprasetyo@unis.ac.id*

Abstract:

The Department of Culture and Tourism, Park and Decoration of the City of Tangerang is a Regional Apparatus Organization that focuses on service to the citizens in terms of Park and decoration in the City of Tangerang. The Department of Culture and Tourism is required to provide maximum service to the citizens. However, in reality, there are still some services that have not been running optimally, one of which is the permission service for the use of parks and green lanes. Existing services still use convoluted procedures because they have not used technology optimally. Therefore, the author conducted research to solve this problem. The results that the authors get is the design of an e-Government system with the concept of a Customer Touching System so that people can do permission administration online. With this system, the process of providing technical recommendations from The Department of Culture and Tourism will take less time. In addition, there are problems with park management. Starting from the cleanliness of the park that is not maintained, the facilities are inadequate. Therefore, with a Customer Relationship Management approach, it is hoped that it can help park management to fix parks in Tangerang City.

Keywords — *Customer Relationship Management, e-Government, Park*

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of communication and information technology (ICT) cannot separate us from the application of these technologies in improving government services to its citizens. One means of improving these services is Electronic Government (e-Government). Effective and efficient services are often used as benchmarks to measure government performance.

The Department of Culture and Tourism, Park and Decoration of the City of Tangerang is a Regional Apparatus Organization that focuses on service to the citizens, which almost all of its activities run from the Tangerang City Regional Budget (APBD). However, in some sectors such as park use services, the Department of Culture and Tourism still collects regional retribution fees for the continuity of the Tangerang City Government's operational activities.

In this research study, the author conducts research on the permission sector for the use of parks and green lanes such as the need for film shooting, bazaars, competitions, and other activities. In this sector, the authors found several problems that could reduce the credibility of the Tangerang City the Department of Culture and Tourism. Starting from the permission service which is convoluted and there is no information on document prerequisites. These problems can be solved if the Department of Culture and Tourism, First and Decorating Division of Tangerang City uses the Customer Touching System which can make it easier for applicants to do permits.

Based on these problems, the author tries to find a solution by designing an e-Government system with a Customer Relationship Management approach so that the level of community satisfaction with services increases. It is also hoped that with this system, the

number of permit applicants and park visitors can increase drastically.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research process includes identification of problems faced by the Department of Culture and Tourism, Park and Decorating Sector of Tangerang City, analysis of ongoing business processes by observation and interviews, identifying needs, modeling data and designing systems by developing prototypes of Electronic Customer Relationship Management (E-CRM).

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a combination of business processes plus technology, which aims to understand various user perspectives. This combination is also useful for distinguishing the competitiveness of products and services (Al-Shammari & Mallouh, 2011). According to O'Brien & Marakas (2011:312), views Customer Relationship Management as a system that integrates with web-based software and databases to support a business process that supports three stages of the relationship between business and customers.

Fig.1. CRM Stage

a) Acquire

A business relies on the support of Customer Relationship Management software and databases to acquire new customers with contact management, prospecting, direct marketing, sales, and fulfillment.

b) Enhance

Web-based Customer Relationship Management account management, customer service, and other supporting tools keep customers happy with superior service. In addition, direct marketing and automating

sales using Customer Relationship Management helps companies in their efforts to increase company profits by doing cross-selling and up-selling.

c) Retain

Customer Relationship Management analytics and database software enables companies to reward their loyal customers, and benefit from the business expansion of these customers.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the design are based on the identification of needs obtained at the Department of Culture and Tourism, Park and Decoration of the City of Tangerang.

3.1 Use Case Diagram

a) Use Case Diagram PTSP Staff

Fig.2. Use Case Diagram PTSP Staff

b) Use Case Diagram Coordinator

Fig.3. Use Case Diagram Coordinator

c) Use Case Diagram Applicant/User

Fig.4. Use Case Diagram Applicant/User

Use Case Diagram in Fig. 2 - 4 describes an interaction between actors and the system, the use case diagram described by the author is adjusted to the needs that have been made.

3.2 Prototype System

The following is a prototype of the e-Government system for permission the use of parks and green lanes in the form of a Web proposal at the Department of Culture and Tourism, Parks and Decorations, Tangerang City.

Fig.5. Dashboard Website

Fig.6. Type of park rental

Fig.6. Contact

Fig.7. Rental data and requirements documents

The Department of Culture and Tourism, the garden and decoration section of the city of tangerang makes it easier for park, applicant to be able to find a list of parks in the city of tangerang and the required documents if they want to rent.

Then if we want to come or ask the park rental department, then this website has provided a clear contact and address.

Fig.8. Permit Form

Fig.9. Compliant Form

To rent a park, the tenant needs to fill out a permit form by filling in the name of the park, type of use, purpose, date of use, number of people, number of usage areas, number of poles, type of applicant and uploading a letter of application. If everything has been filled in, the Applicant submits the document on this website.

While the complaint feature serves to input complaints on dissatisfaction with the condition of the park after use, this is so that the park party from the Department of Culture and Tourism responds to the aspirations and suggestions of the problems faced by the Applicant.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

After studying the problems faced by the Department of Culture and Tourism, Park and Decoration of Tangerang City from the solutions offered, several conclusions can be drawn which can be detailed as follows:

- Permission that initially took a long time can become much more efficient because the applicant does not have to wait long because the application process can be via the web without having to come to the PTSP.
- If previously many applicants came with less prerequisite conditions, with this system the applicant can find out the required requirements.
- There is service feedback and complaints from applicants can help PTSP evaluate its performance and make park permit applicants more comfortable.

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